

URBANIZATION PROCESSES IN THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF CENTRAL ASIA DURING THE BRONZE AGE

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ABSTRACT

In this article analyzed the issues of the formation and development of the urban development culture of the inhabitants of the farming culture of the Bronze Age, who lived in the southern regions of Central Asia, and the reflection of urbanization processes in the material culture.

Keywords: *Urbanization, Bronze age, settlement patterns, socio-economic changes, cultural evolution, material culture, trade networks, technological advances, Bactria, Margiana, historical geography.*

INTRODUCTION. In the Bronze Age, the first farming culture of natural irrigation farming settled in the southern regions of Central Asia. The source of socio-economic and ethno-cultural development of the Bronze Age society appeared in the IV millennium BC. The bronze age of the ancient history of Central Asia covered the III-II millennia BC, and the culture of urban planning was formed [1]. Monuments of this period are Togolok, Gonur, Oltin-tepe, Kelleli, Tahirboy, Auchin in South Turkmenistan; Dashtli 1, 3 in Northern Afghanistan; Sopollitepe and Djarkutan in South Uzbekistan were studied in archeological researchs. A large number of findings found as a result of excavations are important for the comprehensive illumination of the Bronze Age architecture of the peoples of Central Asia. [2, pp. 748-758]

MAIN PART. In general, during the Bronze Age, Margiana and Bactria were densely populated areas. The location and features of the settlements reflect the high level of the lifestyle of the first peasants, testifying to the acceleration of urbanization processes, the emergence of administrative-ideological centers and majestic architecture, and the separate processes of craft separation [3, pp. 25-31]. Analyzing the results of the research, it can be concluded that these large areas were inhabited by unions of settled farming tribes. In this process, oases developed through the establishment of political associations such as city-states or name associations.

By typologically analyzing the majestic architectural structures of the Bronze Age of Bactria and Margiana, the following conclusions can be reached:

I. Structures with a circular plan; (Dashtli 3 temple, Kutlugtepe, Atchapar)

II. Structures with a rectangular plan;

a) In the structure of the pile in front of the rooms where the row is located; (Kelleli – 4, Sopollitepa, etc.)

b) In the structure of the yard in front of various rooms and corridors; (Kelleli – 3, Gonur Palace, Dashli – 3 Palace, Altin 10 and etc.)

2. Rectangular structures with circular towers in the corners;

a) Based on external construction; (Togolok - 1, Dashtli - 1 and etc.)

b) Structures with a square structure in the center; (Gonur Temple, Tilla Tepe and etc.) [4, p. 91].

It is observed that most researchers who have conducted research on the main factors of the urban processes and the level of development in the society have different interpretations of the concept of "first city" or "city" in different periods that are not related to each other. It should be noted that most researchers (A. Askarov, V. Masson, B. Litvinsky, I., Dyakonov, T. Shirinov, B. Udemurodov, I. Masimov, etc.) define the beginning of the foundations of urbanistic processes in Central Asia with the Eneolithic - Bronze Age [5, pp. 569-574].

First of all, it should be noted that the essence and content of the concept of "Urbanization" ("urbanization", "emergence and development of cities" or "urban

planning culture"), which is often found in historical, scientific and sociological literature, is interpreted differently by researchers, and a single concept not created [6, pp. 3-10]. We can conditionally divide specialists who have conducted research in this direction into the following groups:

Foreign researchers. They emphasize in their scientific work that Urbanization is in the leading position in the development of society, and recognize villages and suburbs as areas within Urbanization (Sjoberg, Trigger, Kristaller, Oppenheim, Weber and others);

Researchers from the former Soviet Union. They used the growth of the number of cities in different regions and the growth of the population of the city as the main criterion for the research in this direction. (V. Masson, B. Litvinsky, M. Dyakonov, E. Rtveladze, A. Sagdullaev and others.). The researchers who belong to this group have taken the processes of migration (movement of the population of a certain area to the cities and back), ancient ways and the processes of international communication as the main criterion for their scientific work. (Sarianidi, Askarov, Shirinov, etc.);

Also, according to the concept of Dyakonov and Yakobson, the first cities of the Ancient East mainly served as the economic and political centers of certain oases, centralizing and redistributing agricultural products grown in the entire oases. That is, this function was implemented by the power of the first state system, and its center was embodied in the structure of the first city: the administrative power was in the palace, and the religious-ideological power was in the temples [7, pp. 18-26.]. That is, the main task of the first cities in the East was to lead the economic life of the first emerging states and direct them towards development. This concept is much closer to reality and is recognized by most researchers. It should be noted that in most cases it can be applied to Egypt and Mesopotamia, where a statehood began to take shape in the third millennium BC. [8, pp. 56-65].

According to the results of archaeological research conducted in recent years, it is confirmed that the development of the first cities had a single plan and that the three-part city structure was not typical for all cities of Central Asia. In our opinion, this

situation is explained by natural-geographical conditions, social-economic and military-political factors [9, pp. 42–48].

In the process of analyzing the history of cities, we can observe that in addition to the central capital cities, there were city-states, agrarian (farming) cities, trade cities (port cities in some regions). [10, pp. 601-604.].

According to the researchers, each historical period has its own concepts of "city" based on the historical cultural processes, specific characteristics and development of that period. For example, "early cities", "ancient cities", "medieval cities" and so on. That's why researchers divide the cities into the oldest, medieval and modern cities, taking into account the characteristics of the urbanization process in different periods [11, pp. 49-54].

A city is a relatively ancient and at the same time the most modern form of territorial settlement of people, and every citizen living in it is naturally interested in its development and development. The emergence of cities, the development of existing ones, with the assimilation of the environment, this process reflects the development and characteristics of the social system. Also, each historical period has its own characteristics of urban planning. [12, pp. 73-76].

CONCLUSION. Despite the fact that the issues of the emergence and development of urbanization processes in Central Asia still require a lot of research, when we summarize and analyze the different opinions of researchers, it becomes clear that it is not appropriate to approach the first, oldest cities from the point of view of the current concept of "city". Because, from the point of view of appearance and formation, as well as from the point of view of the main features and functions of urban planning, the first cities are sharply different from the modern, even medieval cities.

Just as the early urban planning culture was formed and developed in different regions of the world in different periods, cities may have performed different tasks in the first period of their emergence or in the developed period, and may have experienced different periods in the process of development at different stages.

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